

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOL. WT., MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Chelate	Metal %		Halogen %		Mol. wt.		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance mohs cm^2 mol^{-1}
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
Fe.L.(H ₂ O) ₂ ⁺ Cl ⁻	12.55	12.4	8.0	7.90	453	499	6.02	65.5
Co.L.(H ₂ O) ₂ ⁺ Cl ⁻	12.85	13.0	8.0	7.85	450	452	0.64	63.5

respectively⁵. The band at 30100 cm^{-1} could be a charge-transfer band. The general absorption in the visible is strong due to a long tail of the band at 30100 cm^{-1} .

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Preparation and Interconversion of Adducts of Copper(II) Benzoate Complex with Picolines and Quinolines

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COMPLEXES of metal carboxylates and their adducts with nitrogen donors have been studied in order to throw light on metal-metal bonding¹ and their anomalous magnetic properties²⁻⁵. Copper (II) benzoate is known to form 1:1 and 1:2 adducts with pyridine^{2,6-8} while 1:1 adduct has also been prepared with quinoline through ligand exchange⁶. It was, therefore considered interesting to prepare adducts of copper (II) benzoate with some more nitrogen heterocyclic ligands such as α -, β -, γ -picolines, quinoline and isoquinoline.

Interaction of copper (II) benzoate with the heterocyclic ligand in 1:1 molar ratio in acetone gives 1:1 adducts while 1:2 adducts are formed when a large excess of the ligand is used. 1:1 Adducts are stable while 1:2 adducts are thermally unstable and give stable 1:1 adducts on heating at 100°-150° or on refluxing in acetone. 1:1 Adducts, on the other hand, on treatment with excess of the ligand in an acetone medium give back 1:2 adducts.

Magnetic and spectral properties of these adducts are being investigated in order to ascertain their precise structures.

Experimental

Anhydrous copper (II) benzoate was prepared as reported earlier⁴. Nitrogen bases were purified by refluxing over potassium hydroxide followed by distillation under reduced pressure. Acetone was dried over fused potassium carbonate. The compounds were characterized by elemental analyses. Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate⁹. Nitrogen was determined microanalytically. The analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Preparation of Adducts

All the adducts listed in Table 1 were prepared by the addition of an equimolar quantity or a large excess of the appropriate heterocyclic ligand to a 0.03M solution of anhydrous copper (II) Benzoate in acetone medium. The solution on standing deposited green or blue crystalline compounds depending on the amount of the ligand used. The compounds were filtered, washed with acetone or acetone containing a little of the appropriate ligand. 1:1 Green adducts were dried at 100°-110° in vacuo while the 1:2 blue adducts were dried at room temperature over conc sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator

Attempts to prepare 1:2 adducts of copper (II) benzoate with α -picoline and quinoline were unsuccessful.

Interconversion of 1:1 and 1:2 Adducts

1:2 Adducts on refluxing in acetone deposited corresponding 1:1 green adducts while 1:1 adducts on standing with a large excess of the ligand in acetone deposited 1:2 blue adducts. The compounds obtained were filtered, washed and dried as before. The purity of the samples was checked by metal analysis.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF ADDUCTS OF COPPER(II) BENZOATE

Sr.No.	Compound	Colour	%Cu		%N	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (α -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	16.14	15.94	3.55	3.51
2.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (β -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	15.80	15.94	3.57	3.51
3.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (γ -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N)	Green	16.07	15.94	3.57	3.51
4.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (Iso-C ₅ H ₇ N)	Green	14.45	14.62	3.48	3.22
5.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (β -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂	Blue	12.64	12.93	6.04	5.70
6.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (γ -CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂	Blue	12.99	12.93	6.04	5.70
7.	Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂ (Iso-C ₅ H ₇ N) ₂	Blue	11.35	11.28	5.13	4.97

An attempt to convert 1 : 1 adduct of isoquinoline into 1 : 2 adduct however has failed.

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Coordination Complexes of Cobalt Chloride with Cinchonine and Quinine

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SINCE after the discovery of vitamin B-12, cobalt chloride is being used in various antianaemic formulations. Malaria is generally followed by anaemia and quinine is an established antimalarial drug. It was therefore, desired to study complexes of cobalt chloride with cinchonine and quinine.

In the literature Vascautanu and Jurca¹ seem to have prepared complexes of cobalt chloride with cinchonine and quinine of the compositions cinchonine₂-(CoCl₂)₃ and quinine-(CoCl₂)₂ and quinine-(CoCl₂)₃.H₂O. These proportions however, do not appear to be convincing. These authors do not seem to have studied the nature of the complexes. Herein we describe the conductometric, spectrophotometric and analytical studies of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Composition and Stability of the complexes :

Cinchonine and quinine were of extra pure grade; cobalt chloride and other materials were of Analar quality.

Preliminary conductometric titrations at 30° ± 0.5° of ligands against cobalt chloride and absorbance studies on 'spekol' of their equimolar solutions using Vosdburgh and Cooper² method indicated 1:1 complexation, λ_{max} for cinchoninecobalt chloride and quinine-cobalt chloride being 345 and 350 nm.

Formation of 1 : 1 complex was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation³, mole ratio⁴ and slope ratio⁵ methods using absorbance as the index property.

The stability constants have been evaluated from Job's curves^{6,7} and Yoe Jones curves⁸ for cinchonine and quinine cobalt chloride complexes. The results are given in Table 1.

Ethanollic solutions of cobalt chloride and ligand were mixed and refluxed on water bath for about 4 hrs when a blue coloured complex was obtained which was cooled, filtered and washed with alcohol and ether.

Cobalt was estimated as tetrapyridine cobalt dithiocyanate⁹ after removing the base, nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's method, chloride as silver chloride and water by heating to 110° till constant weight. The results are given in Table 2.

All these results point to analogous compositions for cobalt chloride complexes of cinchonine and quinine. Considering the fact that each of the two nitrogen and the oxygen of the secondary alcoholic group in the molecules of cinchonine and quinine

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